

Supplemental Figure 1. Analysis of genome-editing event using Sanger sequencing data with Synthego ICE tool (<https://ice.synthego.com/>). “Traces” tab (A) and “contribution” tab (B) are showed for each edited cell line. **A.** “Trace” tab shows edited and wild-type (control) sequences in the region around the guide sgRNA cut. The horizontal black underlined region represents the guide sequence. The horizontal red underline is the PAM site. The vertical black dotted line represents the actual cut site. Cutting and error-prone repair usually results in mixed sequencing bases after the cut, which are represented as a mix chromatogram pick. **B.** “Contribution” tab shows the inferred sequences present in the edited population, explaining the type of edit (indel) and its relative proportion (contribution). Cut sites are represented by black vertical dotted lines, nucleotides that have been deleted are indicated by a dash, and letter 'N' indicates a mix chromatogram pick.

<i>SIKI</i>	CACTTATGCCGGTTCAGACA	GGG	96
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A.

B.

INDEL	CONTRIBUTION	SEQUENCE
-1	89%	G T G A A G G A C A C T T A T G C C G G T T C A - A C A G G G A C A C G T T T C T T C G A C A T C A G C T T G C C C G A G A A G A T T C A G T C T
-1	4%	G T G A A G G A C A C T T A T G C C G G T T C A G - C A G G G A C A C G T T T C T C T T C G A C A T C A G C T T G C C C G A G A A G A T T C A G T C T
-2	3%	G T G A A G G A C A C T T A T G C C G G T T C - - A C A G G G A C A C G T T T C T T C T T C G A C A T C A G C T T G C C C G A G A A G A T T C A G T C T

<i>SIKI</i>	CGCCATGTAAGTGTCCCCGGGGG	CCC	96
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A.

B.

INDEL	CONTRIBUTION	SEQUENCE
-1	93%	C A C C G C G C C A T G T A A G T G T C C C C G G G - G G C C C A G G A G G A C A C C G G T G G A T A G G C T T A C G G T C G A C G T G A G G G T G G G
-2	3%	C A C C G C G C C A T G T A A G T G T C C C C G G G - - G C C C A G G A G G A C A C C G G T G G A T A G G C T T A C G G T C G A C G T G A G G G T G G G

Gene	sgRNA	PAM sequence	% efficiency
<i>DUSPI</i>	TACTAGCGTCCCTGACAGCG	AAT	91

A.

B.

INDEL	CONTRIBUTION	SEQUENCE
+1	77%	CTGAGTACTAGCGTCCCTGACAGCG : NCGGAATCTGGGTGCA GTTCTTGCAGTACCCCACTCTACGATCAGGTTAG
-2	7%	CTGAGTACTAGCGTCCCTGACAGC : -GGAATCTGGGTGCA GTTCTTGCAGTACCCCACTCTACGATCAGGTTAGT
-2	6%	CTGAGTACTAGCGTCCCTGACAGCG : -GGAATCTGGGTGCA GTTCTTGCAGTACCCCACTCTACGATCAGGTTAGT
-6	1%	CTGAGTACTAGCGTCCCTGAC : -GGAATCTGGGTGCA GTTCTTGCAGTACCCCACTCTACGATCAGGTTAGT
-2	1%	CTGAGTACTAGCGTCCCTGACAG : CGGAATCTGGGTGCA GTTCTTGCAGTACCCCACTCTACGATCAGGTTAGT

Gene	sgRNA	PAM sequence	% efficiency
<i>DUSPI</i>	CGTCCAGCAACACCACGGCG	TAG	91

A.

B.

INDEL	CONTRIBUTION	SEQUENCE
+1	65%	GCCGCCCTGCTGGCCGGCGCTACCA : NCCCGTGGTGTGCTGGACGAGCGCAGCGCCGCCCTGGACGGCGCCAAAG
-1	22%	GCCGCCCTGCTGGCCGGCGCTACCA : -GCCGTGGTGTGCTGGACGAGCGCAGCGCCGCCCTGGACGGCGCCAAAGC
-30	2%	GCCGCCCTGCTGGCCGG : -AGCGCAGCGCCGCCCTGGACGGCGCCAAAGC
-6	1%	GCCGCCCTGCTGGCCGGCGCTACCA : -GGTGTGCTGGACGAGCGCAGCGCCGCCCTGGACGGCGCCAAAGC
-2	1%	GCCGCCCTGCTGGCCGGCGCTACCA : -CCGTGGTGTGCTGGACGAGCGCAGCGCCGCCCTGGACGGCGCCAAAGC